

Zeta Gem (P 10.150d) p=1.270 d=435.0pc E(B-V)=0.040; $IR_{ex} = 0.340 \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{0.339(1.2-\lambda)}} - 0.5 \right)$ mag

